

EARTH SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF INFORMATIVENESS OF ATMOSPHERIC ARIDITY INDICES

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Abstract

Prediction of drought, a dangerous hydrometeorological phenomenon, is based on meteorological data (temperature, precipitation, air pressure, dew point, evaporation), combined into a single formula – an index describing the qualitative state of aridity depending on the quantitative value of the index in a given climatic region. Due to the lack of a universal definition of drought, different aridity indices provide an effective assessment of aridity in different climatic regions of the world in different ways. In order to adapt methods for assessing aridity in a specific climatic region accounting for both the physical mechanism of the occurrence and evolution of drought and the influence of geographical and climatic features of the region under study, it is necessary to investigate the informativeness of a particular aridity index in relation to that region. This paper provides a solution for prediction of drought for the Central Asian region.

Keywords: aridity indices, reanalysis, precipitation, temperature, gamma function, cumulative probability, informativeness, amount of information.

Introduction. Atmospheric aridity, a natural component of the climate, can occur in its extreme manifestation, called drought, in any part of the planet [9]. On a global scale, atmospheric drought occurs annually in a particular geographical area and inherently belongs to the category of natural hazards, having a negative impact on various economic sectors and environment.

Various indices are used in scientific research and practical work of meteorological organizations in order to quantify the degree of aridity of a certain period of the year (monthly, seasonal, semi-annual, annual). An overview of their use in meteorological research and practical work is given in [10].

McKee et al. [14] pioneered agrometeorological research for drought monitoring. The Standardized precipitation index (SPI) recommended by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) is then widely used, supplementing the previously widely used Normalized Normalized precipitation index (NPI). The Hydrometeorological Service of the Russian Federation uses the index of Pedyas [5], Selyaninov [8], moisture coefficient of Ivanov [2]. Petrov's aridity index was widely used in the studies of various Uzbek scientists [6]. The Palmer index is widely used in non-CIS countries [12].

Purpose of the work is to investigate the informativeness of the aridity indices, namely, the standardized precipitation index SPI, the normalized NPI index, the Pedy index Si, the aridity index K developed by Petrov, applied to the Central Asian region.

In this work, time series of reanalysis ERA5 [15] of average monthly precipitation, air temperature, relative humidity and dew point with a grid step of 2.5x2.5° from 1948 to 2019 for the territory bounded by latitudes 37.5–47.5° N and longitudes 55–75° E, was used.

Aridity indices. To adapt the methods of assessing aridity for the Central Asian region, we will consider the above listed indices in more detail.

The SPI index. The idea of presenting the aridity index in a standardized form leads to the expression of a transformed cumulative probability [13,14]

$$H(p) = q + (1 - q) \cdot G(p), \quad (1)$$

where q - is the probability of zero precipitation, and

$$G(p) = \int_0^p g(p) dp = \frac{1}{\beta^a \Gamma(a)} \int_0^p p^a \exp\left(-\frac{p}{\beta}\right) dp. \quad (2)$$

In $G(p)$ is the cumulative probability distribution function, $G(a)$ is the gamma function – Γ , β are the scale and shape parameters. In [1] it is shown that the gamma function approximating the empirical distribution can be replaced without loss of accuracy by a polynomial of the n th degree, which, firstly, greatly simplifies the computational process, and, secondly, eliminates mathematical incorrectness, because at zero values the gamma function is not defined.

Taking into account (2), the CPI index itself is calculated based on the ratio [14]

$$SPI = m \left[\frac{1}{(k - H(p))^2} \times \frac{c_0 + c_1 t + c_2 t^2}{1 + d_1 t + d_2 t^2 + d_3 t^3} \right] \quad (3)$$

In (3) $t = 1/[k - H(p)]^2$, the sign "-" for $0 < H(p) \leq 0.5$; the sign "+" for $0.5 < H(p) < 1$; $k=0$ for $0 < H(p) \leq 0.5$ and $k=1$ at $0.5 < H(p) < 1$; $c_i, d_j = \text{const}$ – even coefficients.

Table 1 shows the classification of the SPI index and the qualitative category by the values of its values.

Table 1

Dryness classification by SPI values		
Code	SPI value	Category
	Dryness	
-4	SPI < -2,00	Extreme
-3	-2,00 ≤ SPI < -1,50	Serious
-2	-1,50 ≤ SPI < -0,99	Moderate
-1	-0,99 ≤ SPI < -0,00	Weak
Humidity		
Code	SPI value	Category
+1	0,00 ≤ SPI < +0,50	Soft
+2	0,50 ≤ SPI < +1,50	Moderate
+3	1,50 ≤ SPI < +2,00	Strong
+4	SPI ≥ +2,00	Extreme

Index of Si. This index, developed by D. A. Pedem in the 50-ies of the last century, characterizes the arid (moist) at the degree of the deviation of the values of temperature $\Delta T = T_i - \bar{T}$ and precipitation $\Delta P = P_i - \bar{P}$ from the climate of Korea norms, standardized by the corresponding variance $\sigma(T), \sigma(P)$:

$$Si = \frac{\Delta T}{\sigma(T)} - \frac{\Delta P}{\sigma(P)}. \tag{5}$$

The ranges of gradations of Si index values corresponding to the qualitative categories of the SPI index are given in Table 2.

Index NIP. The normalized precipitation index was used in hydrometeorological services before the introduction of the SPI index into widespread practice, which represents a deviation from the norm of precipitation P_i , normalized to the climatic norm:

$$NIP = \frac{P_i - \bar{P}}{\bar{P}} \tag{6}$$

Table 2

Aridity classification by Si values		
Code	Si value	Category
	Humidity	
+4	$S_i > 4,5$	Soft
+3	$4,5 \geq S_i \geq 3,1$	Moderate
+2	$2,1 < S_i \leq 3,0$	Strong
+1	$1,1 < S_i \leq -2,0$	Extreme
Dryness		
Code	Si value	Category
-1	$-1,0 < S_i \leq +1,0$	Extreme
-2	$-2,0 \leq S_i \leq -1,1$	Serious
-3	$-3,0 \leq S_i < -2,1$	Moderate
-4	$S_i \leq -3,1$	Weak

The ranges of aridity (Humidity) of the NIP index corresponding to the qualitative categories of aridity (humidity) of the SPI index are given in Table 3,

Table 3

Aridity classification by NIP values		
Code	SPI value	Category
	Dryness	
-4	$NIP < -4,00$	Extreme
-3	$-4,00 \delta NIP < -1,80$	Serious
-2	$-1,80 \delta NIP < -0,80$	Moderate
-1	$-0,80 \delta NIP < -0,00$	Weak
Humidity		
Code	SPI value	Category
+1	$0,00 \delta NIP < +2,00$	Soft
+2	$2,00 \delta NIP < +4,00$	Moderate
+3	$4,00 \delta NIP < +5,00$	Strong
+4	$NIP \geq +5,00$	Extreme

Index K. The thermohydrimetric coefficient K of air dryness with constant moisture retention developed by Uzbek scientist Petrov, describes a tendency to increase dryness with increasing air temperature, and with constant temperature and an increase in moisture

content - a tendency to decrease dryness (Fig. 1). The index is calculated by the following formula:

$$K = \frac{T - \tau}{T} \% \tag{6}$$

where T is the air temperature (K), τ is the dew point (K).

Table 4 shows the classification of the K index according to the degree of aridity (humidity).

Fig. 1. a) – Surface index K as a function of dew point and temperature; б) – as a function of RH of dew point and relative humidity; c) – K-index curves as a function of temperature at constant relative humidity; д) – as a function of relative humidity at constant temperature.

Research methodology. The absolute and relative informativeness of the aridity indices is considered from the standpoint of the information theory described in [4]. For a random variable X having a finite number of values with probabilities $p(X_i) = p_i, p_i \geq 0, \sum_i p_i = 1$, the intrinsic information $I_X = -\sum p_i \log_2 p_i$ is itself a random variable other than its average value – the Shannon information entropy $H(X_i) = -\sum p_i \log_2 p_i$.

In this case, $H_{max} = \log_2 N$ (if the probabilities of the outcomes of events are equal; N is the total number of implementations of a random variable). The smaller the entropy value, the less additional information is required for an adequate assessment of the state of the system. The information has the property of additivity, i.e. for independent variables $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ the equality

$$I(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n I_i.$$

Table 4

Aridity classification by K values			
Code	Category	Humidity RH, %	Index K, %о
Aridity			
-4	Extreme	RH ≤ 30	K > 65
-3	Serious	30 < RH ≤ 40	65 ≥ K > 45
-2	Moderate	40 < RH ≤ 45	45 ≥ K > 35
-1	Weak	45 < RH ≤ 50	35 ≥ K > 30
Humidity			
+1	Soft	50 < RH ≤ 60	30 ≥ K > 20
+2	Moderate	60 < RH ≤ 70	20 ≥ K > 15
+3	Strong	70 < RH ≤ 85	15 ≥ K > 5
+4	Extreme	85 < RH ≤ 100	K ≤ 5

We introduce into consideration two systems X and Y , the states of which $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$ и $y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N$ are determined by the values of the aridity indices, respectively. The absolute amount of I_A , information contained in each of the systems is

$$I_A = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 p_i}{H_{max}} \tag{7}$$

where p_i is the verticality of the i state of the system ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$).

The relative informativeness of I_O system Y in relation to system X is estimated by the following formula

$$I_O = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i(X_i) \sum_{j=1}^m p_j^i(X_i) \log_2 p_j^i(X_i) - \sum_{k=1}^n p_k(Y_k) \sum_{j=1}^m p_j^k(Y_k|X_i) \log_2 p_j^k(Y_k|X_i)}{H_{max}} \tag{8}$$

In expression (8), $p_j^k(Y_k|X_i)$ is the conditional probability of the k -th gradation of system Y , provided that system X gave the i -th gradation.

Taking into account the widespread use of the SPI index based on the recommendation of the WMO in studies of drought processes in various geographical areas worldwide, the informativeness of the Si, NIP, K indices in this work is estimated relative to the SPI index (relative informativeness). For this purpose, absolute and relative informativity were calculated according to formulas (7), (8) and taking the implementation of the SPI index as a system X and the implementation of the NPI, Si, K indices sequentially as a system Y . The pre-calculated time series of indices were attributed to one school scale with a code for each category of aridity (humidity), as shown in Table 6.

Calculation results. Each of the considered dryness indices is closely correlated with the other. Table 5 shows the mutual correlation matrix of their interrelation, calculated from the original and reduced to the same scale data. Thus, each of the listed indices can be used for the region of Uzbekistan to diagnose the state of aridity. This is confirmed by the assessment of their informativeness shown in Table 6, which presents the probabilities of the p_i categories of the indices under consideration and their absolute I_A and relative I_O amount of information calculated from samples of ERA5 reanalysis of temperature, precipitation and dew point over a 70-year period for all months of the year in the above-mentioned territory. As follows from the table, the quantitative estimates of the informativeness of all indices given to the same scale are very close. At the same time, however, the SPI index is the most informative, which confirms the decision of the WMO to use it in the work of hydrometeorological services.

Table 5

Correlation matrix of aridity indices				
Index	SPI	Si	NPI	K
According to the initial data				
SPI	1,00	0,95	0,99	0,92
Si		1,00	0,98	0,78
NIP			1,00	0,88
K				1,00
According to the data provided				
SPI	1,00	0,86	0,86	0,87
Si		1,00	0,92	0,73
NIP			1,00	0,82
K				1,00

Table 6

Probabilities of aridity indices categories and their absolute amount of information (AAI)						
Type	Category	Code	Unconditional probabilities			
			SPI	Si	NIP	K
Foordrynes	Extreme	-4	0,079	0,008	0,002	0,356
	Serious	-3	0,313	0,020	0,006	0,077
	Moderate	-2	0,424	0,040	0,014	0,081
	Weak	-1	0,184	0,072	0,050	0,071
Hopma Standard		0	0,000	0,141	0,165	0,078
Humidity	Soft	1	0,000	0,459	0,368	0,075
	Moderate	2	0,000	0,248	0,318	0,089
	Strong	3	0,000	0,012	0,074	0,106
	Extreme	4	0,000	0,000	0,003	0,067
AKH			0,564	0,669	0,678	0,904
OKH			□	0,564	0,669	0,678

Potentially dangerous factors contributing to the occurrence of atmospheric drought, against the background of synoptic processes, are determined by the local features of the geographical area, which is characterized by a variability of landscapes. The characteristic landscapes of the territory of Uzbekistan are represented by deserts, steppes, mountain ranges. There are four distinct landscapes [11]: deserts and plains (chul),

foothills and hills (adyr), mountains (tau), highlands (jailau). In turn, these landscapes are subdivided into 12 agro-climatic districts on the basis of agro-climatic zoning (Fig. 1) [7]. In general, this diversity can be generalized as lowland and sub-mountain regions, which, with established circulation processes, determine the degree of risk of potentially dangerous factors for the occurrence of drought.

Fig. 1. Agro-climatic zoning of the territory of Uzbekistan.

Figure 2 shows the spatial climatic distribution of the average monthly values of the aridity index SPI, and Figure 3 shows seasonal, semi-annual, annual and during the growing season on the territory of Uzbekistan and neighboring countries. As follows from Fig. 2, 3, the driest months in climatic terms fall on June–October and the summer season, which is fully consistent with long-term observations [3]. At the same time, in the autumn season and the second half of the year, areas of aridity are distinguished, capturing the Nizhneamudarya and Aral agro-climatic districts with a negative maximum SPI in the Nizhneamudarya ($SPI = -0.25$). Relative to other districts, the greatest aridity is characteristic of the agro-climatic district of Ustyurt in March, and in the summer season there is increased humidity relative to other districts. This feature of the spatial distribution of the SPI index is a consequence of the isolation of the synoptic processes and the terrain landscape of the western part of the territory of Uzbekistan, manifested in the fact that during the hot period of the year, the western and north-western intrusions are eroded when passing through the territory to the east.

As follows from the obtained distributions of SPI and agro-climatic zoning of the territory of Uzbekistan, in general, their good agreement can be noted, which

implies its sufficient informativeness in relation to the assessment of the risk of aridity in a particular geographical area. The latter indicates that SPI can be successfully used in the task of monitoring aridity.

Conclusions. The indices of aridity (humidification) considered in this work, almost equally well describe the state of dryness on the territory of Uzbekistan and neighboring countries. The most informative of them is the SPI index, which once again indicates the correctness of the WMO recommendation for its use in scientific and practical work.

Modification of the cumulative probability into the expression of the aridity index SPI by replacing the gamma function with a polynomial of the n th degree greatly simplifies the computational process and establishes the mathematical correctness of the expression.

The above-mentioned aridity indices, due to their high informativeness, can be used in solving the problem of monitoring aridity on the territory of Uzbekistan and neighboring countries. The creation of a system for monitoring fluctuations in humidity and dry periods makes it possible to correctly approach the problem of forecasting monthly, seasonal, semi-annual, annual and for the growing season of drought.

Fig. 2. Climatic spatial distribution of average monthly values of the SPI index.

Fig. 3.

Climatic spatial distribution of seasonal, semi-annual, annual and vegetation period values of the SPI index.

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